

Side-chain Alkylation of Toluene with Methanol over Single Zeolite Catalysts

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Manuscript received 5 January 1996, revised 28 June 1996, accepted 25 September 1996

The side-chain alkylation of toluene with methanol has been studied over a number of prospective zeolite catalysts, such as Na-X, Cs-X and Cs-B-X at atmospheric pressure in a fixed-bed reactor. Cs-X zeolite showed a higher activity than Cs-B-X and Na-X zeolites with respect to toluene conversion and yield of styrene. The effects of reaction temperature and molecular ratios of reactants have been investigated. The maximum toluene conversion of 25.5% and styrene to ethylbenzene mole ratio of 4 : 1 are obtained with Cs-X zeolite. The catalysts show good stability as found with time-on-stream studies.

The side-chain alkylation of toluene with methanol synthesising styrene offers an economically attractive process for commercial production of styrene¹. It is not only a one-step process but also this method offers the advantage of lower raw material cost compared to the traditional Friedel-Crafts alkylation of benzene with ethylene to synthesise intermediate ethylbenzene for styrene production.

Sidorenko *et al.*² first reported the side-chain alkylation of toluene with methanol to form styrene, and since then a number of publications³⁻⁶ have appeared on various aspects of the side-chain alkylation reaction. Zeolites as well as non-zeolite catalysts have been used for this alkylation reaction. Sodesawa *et al.*⁴ used metal phosphate, such as BPO₄, Zr₃(PO₄)₄, Ca(PO₄)₂, Na₃PO₄ on activated carbon, K₃PO₄ on activated carbon as well as SiO₂-Al₂O₃ and MgO. Brulyants and Garten⁶ developed a basic compound catalyst selected from oxides and/or hydroxides of Li, Na, K, Rb, Cs, Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba to be used for alkylation of toluene with formaldehyde to manufacture styrene. Among the above catalysts only MgO and CsOH-SiO₂ showed some side-chain alkylation activity though the yield of styrene was very low. Compared to the above catalysts, X and Y type zeolites exchanged with alkali cations showed better side-chain alkylation activity first reported by Sidorenko *et al.*² and later confirmed by Yashima *et al.*³. Furthermore, X type is more active than other zeolites according to the published literature⁷. However, it is evident that the work done so far in this area has the main aim of understanding the mechanism of the conversion of toluene to styrene under the influence of a variety of catalysts and their combinations. Not much work has been done to translate this novel type of reaction for eventual industrial use mainly due to low yield of styrene and substantial ethylbenzene formation that makes this reaction less attractive for eventual commercial exploitation.

The objective of the present study was to find out a suitable single zeolite catalyst or a modified single zeolite to maximise styrene formation at the expense of ethylbenzene and to optimise the process parameters that will

favour the side-chain alkylation reaction leading to high yield of styrene.

Results and Discussion

The side-chain alkylations of toluene with methanol were carried out over various single zeolite systems, viz. Na-X, Cs-X and Cs-B-X zeolites in a fixed-bed unit under varying ratios of reactants (toluene : methanol = 5 : 1 to 1 : 5) and in the temperature range 375–450° at atmospheric pressure. The other reaction conditions were maintained constant throughout the experiment with a constant space time,

$$W/F = 3.1 \times 10^4 \text{ g cat s mol}^{-1}, \text{ where}$$

$$W/F = \frac{\text{mass of the catalyst}}{\text{feed rate of (toluene + methanol) (mol s}^{-1}\text{)}}$$

and a constant carrier gas (N₂) flow of 1.0 dm³ min⁻¹.

The conversion of reactants, yields and selectivities of the products were calculated as follows :

$$\text{Conversion (mole \%)} = \frac{\text{Moles of aromatic products}}{\text{Moles of (aromatic product + unconverted reactant)}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Yield (mole \%)} = \frac{\text{Moles of aromatic product}}{\text{Moles of reactant fed}} \times 100$$

$$\% \text{Selectivity} = \frac{\text{Moles of aromatic product}}{\text{Moles of (ethylbenzene + styrene)}} \times 100$$

Reaction temperature : The effect of reaction temperature on the side-chain alkylation of toluene with methanol on Na-X, Cs-X and Cs-B-X zeolites was examined in the temperature range 375–450° under a constant mole ratio of reactants, i.e. toluene-to-methanol ratio of 1 : 5. The results are shown in Table 1. At 375°, the side-chain alkylation reaction was insignificant. With increase in the reaction temperature side-chain alkylation became predominant and

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF REACTION TEMPERATURE ON SIDE-CHAIN ALKYLATION OF TOLUENE WITH VARIOUS ZEOLITE CATALYSTS

	Na-X				Cs-X				Cs-B-X			
	375°	400°	425°	450°	375°	400°	425°	450°	375°	400°	425°	450°
Conversion (mole%):												
Toluene	1.5	4.66	8.2	8.6	7.23	16.1	25.5	27.18	6.27	15.59	25.1	26.58
Yield (mole %):												
Styrene	0.83	2.5	4.2	4.42	5.83	12.5	20.0	20.67	5.17	12.17	19.2	19.58
Ethylbenzene	0.66	2.08	3.5	4.0	1.33	3.33	5.08	5.83	1.0	3.17	5.7	6.33
% Selectivity:												
Styrene	55.55	54.55	54.3	52.5	81.4	78.95	79.7	78.0	83.78	79.36	77.2	75.56
Ethylbenzene	44.44	45.45	45.7	47.5	18.6	21.05	20.3	22.0	16.22	20.64	22.8	24.44

*Toluene : Methanol mole ratio = 1 : 5.

the yield of styrene increased substantially upto 425°. On increasing the temperature upto 450° the yields of side-

chain alkylation products increased further but the rate of fouling of the zeolite catalyst increased considerably resulting in decreased activity with time-on-stream. Hence the most suitable reaction temperature is 425° in accordance with the published literature^{3,7} in respect of yield of side-chain alkylation products specially styrene as well as the retention of the activity of the catalysts with time-on-stream.

Fig. 1. Change of activity with time-on-stream over Cs-X-zeolite: (o) toluene, (Δ) styrene, (●) ethylbenzene; reaction temp. = 425°, toluene : methanol mole ratio = 1 : 5.

Molecular ratios of reactants : A wide variation of mole ratios of the reactants, viz. 5 : 1 to 1 : 5 of toluene-to-methanol was employed to study the side-chain alkylation reaction for each set of catalyst for evaluation. The results (Table 2) indicate that at higher mole ratio of toluene-to-methanol there were less of side-chain alkylation reactions to give styrene and ethylbenzene but some disproportionation of toluene to benzene and xylenes were observed. As the mole ratios of toluene-to-methanol decreased the conversion of toluene increased with the formation of higher amounts of side-chain alkylation products as well as increase in styrene yield. Thus the desired reaction proceeds best at high methanol-to-toluene ratio of 5 : 1 at which the undesired side-reactions are prevented and a higher styrene-to-ethylbenzene ratio is obtained.

Activities of Na-X and ion-exchanged zeolites : Though the side-chain alkylation is taking place with Na-X zeolite

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF MOLECULAR RATIOS OF TOLUENE-TO-METHANOL ON SIDE-CHAIN ALKYLATION OF TOLUENE WITH VARIOUS ZEOLITE CATALYSTS*

	Na-X					Cs-X					Cs-B-X				
	5:1	3:1	1:1	1:3	1:5	5:1	3:1	1:1	1:3	1:5	5:1	3:1	1:1	1:3	1:5
Conversion (mol %):															
Toluene	—	—	3.6	6.35	8.2	—	—	15.08	21.35	25.5	—	—	14.83	21.18	25.1
Methanol	0.83	1.95	—	—	—	6.2	9.75	—	—	—	5.5	9.32	—	—	—
Yield (mole %):															
Styrene	0.37	0.99	1.83	3.33	4.2	4.46	7.42	11.66	16.66	20	3.88	6.8	11	16	19.2
Ethylbenzene	0.37	0.90	1.67	2.91	3.5	1.4	2.0	3.16	4.33	5.08	1.46	2.3	3.6	3.6	4.83
Benzene	0.008	0.007	—	—	—	0.125	0.083	—	—	—	0.042	0.015	—	—	—
Xylene	0.008	0.005	—	—	—	0.144	0.079	—	—	—	0.038	0.017	—	—	—
% Selectivity:															
Styrene	50	51.84	52.4	53.3	54.3	76.43	78.76	78.65	79.36	79.7	72.66	74.54	75.4	76.8	77.2
Ethylbenzene	50	48.16	47.6	46.7	45.7	29.57	21.24	21.34	20.64	20.3	27.34	25.45	24.6	23.2	22.8

*Reaction temp. = 425°

as claimed by various workers^{3,8}, the activity of Na-X zeolite is rather low as has been shown in our present study. The low overall conversion of toluene and yields of side-chain alkylation products clearly indicate that Na-X zeolite does not show much promise as possible side-chain alkylation catalyst. With other single zeolites it is seen that Cs-X is quite effective and the Cs-B-X is slightly less effective compared to Cs-X as the side-chain alkylation catalysts. There was no improvement in the catalytic activity in side-chain alkylation using boron as promoter in Cs-B-X zeolite in comparison to Cs-X zeolite catalyst whereas earlier workers⁹ reported an improvement in side-chain alkylation with Cs-B-X catalyst. Therefore, the activities of various single zeolite catalysts for side-chain alkylation decreased in the following sequence : Cs-X > Cs-B-X \gg Na-X. Furthermore, it has been observed that the yield of styrene is far better than the non-zeolite catalysts^{4,6} used earlier, e.g. 0.7 and 1% styrene yield was obtained with MgO and CsOH-SiO₂ catalysts respectively.

Fig. 2. Change of activity with time-on-stream over Cs-B-X zeolite : (●) toluene, (Δ) styrene (O) ethylbenzene, reaction temp. = 425°, toluene : methanol mole ratio = 1 : 5.

Change in the catalyst activity : Figs. 1 and 2 show the changes in the activities of Cs-X and Cs-B-X zeolites with time-on-stream respectively. It is seen that the activities towards side-chain alkylation remains fairly constant over a period of about 6 h run on stream and then a slight fall of activity is observed due to carbon deposition on the catalysts. Further, the above catalysts could be regenerated by burning off the carbon deposited on the catalyst with oxygen and the catalysts showed side-chain alkylation activity comparable to the fresh catalysts.

Experimental

Synthesis grade toluene and methanol (99% purity, E. Merck) were used as such.

Catalyst preparation : Single ion-exchanged zeolite, Cs-X, was prepared by ion-exchange of commercial X-type (Na-X) zeolite (Associated Cement Companies Ltd., India) in the form of 1.5 mm cylindrical pellets. Zeolites precalcined at 500° for 2 h was treated with 0.45 N aqueous cesium hydroxide solution at room temperature. The exchanged zeolite was then filtered and washed with distilled water until the pH of the washed solution reaches about 8. The ion-exchanged catalyst was then dried and activated at 110° and 500° respectively for 4 h.

The incorporation of boron (0.8% wt B) was done according to the reported procedure¹⁰. Boric acid (0.92 g) was dissolved in acetone (300 ml). Cs-X zeolite (20 g) was treated with this solution for 3 h at room temperature. The acetone was then removed by filtration and the modified Cs-B-X zeolite was dried at 110° for 3 h.

The dosage of alkali metal ion in the zeolite was determined using a Varian 575 BQ atomic absorption spectrometer. The catalyst contained 10.97 weight % Cs. The specific surface areas of the zeolites Na-X and Cs-X were 281.1 and 202.7 m² g⁻¹ respectively, as determined by B.E.T. method. Samples of zeolite were subjected to X-ray analysis to ensure that the crystal structure was retained after exchange. The addition of boron to the ion-exchanged zeolite did not show any loss of crystallinity.

Procedure : The performance of the catalysts was examined in a fixed-bed flow reactor at atmospheric pressure. The catalyst was activated by calcination in a flow of nitrogen gas at 500° for 2 h and brought to the reaction temperature *in situ*. Nitrogen also served as carrier gas. When the reactor and the vaporiser attained the desired temperature, a mixture of toluene and methanol was fed continuously to the vaporiser dropwise by mercury displacement method and the vapour of the reactants was carried to the catalyst bed after mixing with the carrier gas. The reactor effluent was condensed using an ice-trap. The liquid product was collected and the gas was released into the atmosphere through the wet gas meter.

The liquid products were analysed on a Nucon GC 5765 gas chromatograph using 5% SP 1200 + 1.75% bentone 34 on 100/120 chromosorb W column and a flame ionization detector were employed.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for granting fellowship to one of them (K.P.).

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